

Examining the Influence of Covid -19 Pandemic on Efficacy of Participative Management in Primary Schools

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ABSTRACT

The paper looked at the consequences of Covid-19 pandemic on participative management in primary schools. The primary focus of the inquiry revolves around the extent to which Covid-19 impacts the effectiveness of participatory management in primary schools. The author argues that the dearth of appropriate strategies to involve students and staff in instructional activities during the pandemic posed some challenges for effective participative management. Literature review was used as a method of data collection. The author analysed the findings of other scholars in understanding the consequences of the pandemic. The instructor attrition, student withdrawals, and drop-outs were attributed to the dread, ambiguity, and fatality rate associated with the virus. The process of engaging teachers and students post lock-down exposed school administration to a situation of being inefficient and unable to restore appropriate educational settings. Because of this, teachers together with school administrators were pressurised to come up with new effective methods to mitigate the class disruptions with the schools.

KEYWORDS: Covid-19 Pandemic, participative management, efficacy, primary schools, educational leadership

INTRODUCTION

The author looked at the influence of the Covid-19 pandemic on the effectiveness of participative management in schools, e.g., in primary schools. The article assumes that the Covid-19 pandemic posed significant challenges to the implementation of participatory management in primary schools. The lack of alternate strategies during lockdown significantly hindered student and teacher inclusion. [1] note that strict lockdown measures, meant to curb the virus, disrupted participative management in primary schools. This unprecedented disruption affected various stakeholders, including principals, administrators, SMTs, teachers, parents, SGBs, and students, posing significant challenges to their involvement in decision-making processes [2]. In this article, "SMT" also refers to the school governing body (SGB).

The pandemic forced school administrators and stakeholders to adapt to challenges like remote learning, disrupted communication, and altered decision-making [3]. Emphasizing participatory leadership is crucial for improving primary school resilience [4]. This approach fosters collaborative decision-making during disruptions. Schools used virtual platforms like Zoom, Google Meet, and Microsoft Teams for live lessons to maintain traditional classroom interactions [5]. However, pre-recorded classes posed challenges due to limited resources, hindering skill and knowledge development [6].

According to [7], the pandemic exacerbated pre-existing technological disparities, making it difficult to effectively include students in the usage of online platforms and collaborative tools. Similarly, [8] warn that the absence of these crucial communication tools, referred to as the digital gap, poses a threat to the inclusion of individuals and impedes the implementation of participatory management in schools. [9] found that the abrupt transition to remote learning led to a decrease in parental participation. This decrease was attributed to many challenges such as work obligations, limited time availability, lack of acquaintance with technology and inadequate knowledge and abilities. Consequently, parents' capacity to assist their children's education at home was constrained.

[10] warned that remote learning has led to significant challenges like reduced student involvement and motivation. [11] found these issues worsened by screen fatigue and

distractions, hindering the development of an active participative culture in primary schools. Teachers and administrators face pressure to create innovative strategies to combat these issues [12]. The pandemic has introduced a "new normal," necessitating agility and adaptation in primary schools to maintain effective participatory management [13].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptualization of Participative Management in primary schools.

Participative management (PM) in primary schools entails collaborative decision-making processes that involve all stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and administrators, in the governance, professional development, and operational aspects of the educational institution. This inclusive approach promotes a feeling of responsibility and ownership, resulting in enhanced educational results within a supportive and favourable school atmosphere that encourages successful teaching and learning. The following principles will serve as the foundation for this process:

- **Inclusivity** which ensures that all stakeholders—teachers, students, parents, and community members—are actively involved in the decision-making process. This principle values diverse perspectives and experiences, promoting a holistic approach to problem-solving and policy development. By including a broad range of voices, schools can create more equitable and effective educational environments.
- **Transparency** in participative management that involves open and honest communication about decisions, processes, and policies. It ensures that all stakeholders have access to relevant information and understand how decisions are made. This openness builds trust and fosters a culture of accountability, as everyone is aware of the criteria and rationale behind decisions.
- **Shared responsibility** which means that all stakeholders share ownership of both the successes and challenges faced by the school. This principle encourages collective action and collaboration, with each member playing an active role in the implementation and evaluation of decisions. Shared responsibility leads to a more engaged and committed community, as everyone feels accountable for the outcomes.

Globally, effective PM has been found to improve student performance by establishing a more engaging and supportive learning environment. Involving teachers and parents in decision-making processes ensures that educational strategies have been tailored to students' specific needs, resulting in more successful teaching and learning practices [14]. For example, schools that utilise PM frequently report increased levels of student motivation, improved academic performance, and better behavioural results. PM is especially important in South Africa since students come from a variety of socioeconomic backgrounds. Effective PM resolves inequities by incorporating community members in the educational process, ensuring that policies and procedures are culturally and contextually relevant [15]. However, the Covid-19 lockdowns created substantial issues for PM. The shift to remote learning has disrupted established communication pathways, making it difficult to maintain inclusive decision-making procedures. An absence of digital connectivity in many rural areas exacerbated these challenges by limiting important stakeholders' participation[16].

Impact of Lockdowns on Participative Management in Primary Schools.

"Lockdown" is a term used to describe an array of emergency protocols that impose restrictions on movement and prohibit entry to public areas in order to control the transmission of contagious illnesses. Globally, the Covid-19 pandemic prompted extensive school closures because of the disruption of conventional teaching methods [17]. In South Africa, these policies exacerbated pre-existing disparities, especially in rural primary schools that lacked digital infrastructure.[18] argues that the transition to remote learning impeded participatory management, a collaborative strategy that involves teachers, parents, students, and administrators working together to make decisions. The absence of internet connection and digital devices greatly impeded efficient communication and interaction among stakeholders [16]. [19] assert that the lack of face-to-face interactions and mentorship possibilities has exacerbated the isolation of teaching practice from students, leading to a significant decline in the quality of guidance and assistance in primary schools. Nevertheless, overcoming these challenges necessitates the allocation of resources towards digital tools and training as well as assuring ongoing and inclusive engagement in the educational processes of primary schools.

School administration during lockdown, global and South African context.

School administration entails a variety of responsibilities, including instructional leadership, personnel management, financial control, and creating a secure learning environment in the primary school setting [20] . Administrators play a critical role in implementing educational policy, managing resources, and developing relationships with stakeholders [21]. However, the Covid-19 pandemic created extraordinary challenges, notably during lockdowns, which had a significant impact on the educational the premises. Globally, lockdowns challenged traditional educational structures, compelling administrators to quickly adjust to remote learning environments. In South Africa, for example, the abrupt shift to online and modular schooling revealed serious infrastructural deficiencies with negative consequences. Many schools lacked adequate technical resources, and administrators struggled to coordinate remote learning modalities [22]. As a result, the digital divide became growing more apparent with rural schools struggling more than their urban counterparts due to restricted internet access and technical equipment.

Similarly, participatory management, a decision-making strategy that involves collaboration among stakeholders such as teachers, parents, and students, was significantly impacted during the lockdowns. Participative management is characterised by the practice of inclusive consultation and group problem-solving in all school-related activities and challenges [23]. Nevertheless, the dynamics were further exacerbated by the social distancing strategies and remote relationships brought forth by the pandemic. In South Africa, school administrators relied extensively on virtual meetings, which, although facilitating ongoing communication, sometimes excluded individuals lacking sufficient digital access, literacy, and technological abilities [24]. This not only impeded the effectiveness of participative management but also brought attention to the existing disparities within the school system. Notwithstanding these challenges, the lockdowns also highlighted the tenacity and flexibility of school administrations. Several administrators creatively utilised existing resources to ensure the uninterrupted provision of education. For instance, certain schools in South Africa utilised radio-based instruction and community outreach projects in order to solve the digital divide [25]. Although not completely replacing traditional participative management approaches, these efforts showed a dedication to inclusive education in the face of challenges.

It is worth emphasising that the Covid-19 lockdowns had an immense effect on school administration, exposing infrastructure weaknesses and testing participative management norms. However, administrators' adaptive answers demonstrated the capacity for resilience and innovation in the face of global paradigm shifts in education.

Effective communication during the lockdown

Efficient communication in participatory management entails an open and honest, clear, and comprehensive discourse that includes all individuals involved. Similarly, it is distinguished by the practice of attentive listening, consciousness, and reciprocal regard, ensuring that all perspectives are considered and valued [26]. This methodology promotes cooperation, improves the process of making decisions, and cultivates a sense of responsibility and ownership among individuals within the team. Effective communication in participative management is essential in the field of education, especially in primary schools. It has a critical role in actively engaging teachers, students, parents, and the wider community in the educational process[27].

The Covid-19 lockdowns had a huge impact on participatory management in South African primary schools by disrupting traditional methods of communication on a global basis. [28] discovered that the shift to distant learning and the need for social distancing posed challenges to face-to-face interactions, which are crucial for participatory management. In South Africa, the digital divide exacerbated these challenges. In a similar vein, numerous primary schools in rural areas had a scarcity of essential infrastructure, such as reliable access to the internet and electronic devices, impeding the efficacy of communication among teachers, students, and parents[29]. Furthermore, the lockdowns exacerbated the isolation experienced by teaching practice students, who depend on mentorship and peer contacts to enhance their professional growth. Consequently, the lack of face-to-face cooperation chances resulted in a decrease in the standard of mentorship and support, which had a detrimental impact on their teaching experience and professional growth [30]. There are various strategies can be utilised to mitigate the challenges of effective communication in

participative management, particularly during periods of lockdown which include the following:

- Providing schools with reliable internet access and digital devices can be helpful to bridge the communication gap. In addition, training teachers, students and parents in using digital tools can also enhance their engagement in the educational processes.
- Regular virtual meetings encompassing online forums and digital feedback mechanisms can also ensure continuous interaction and involvement of all stakeholders.
- The implementation of blended learning approaches, combining online and in-person methods are essential because they can offer flexibility and maintain effective communication even during disruptions.

Teachers' roles during the lockdown.

Teachers worldwide faced great obstacles that redefined their roles in education during the Covid-19 pandemic lockdowns. Distance learning required swift adaptation to digital platforms, rethinking teaching methods, and increased responsibility for addressing students' emotional and academic needs [31]. This transformative epoch highlighted teachers' role in educational continuity and participatory school management. Thus, teachers' technological adoption was crucial during lockdown. Teachers must learn virtual classrooms, online collaboration technologies, and digital evaluation systems overnight [32]. This transition required technical skills and creative remote student engagement. According to & [33] primary school teachers now lead online conversations, create multimedia learning tools, and organise virtual group activities on virtual platforms. Their ability to handle these problems affected how well schools maintained participatory management structures.

Lockdowns isolated students, but teachers helped them stay healthy. In addition to their academic duties, they provided comfort, understanding, and constancy to students at times of uncertainty [34]. Virtual check-ins, customised assignment comments, and virtual office hours helped teachers maintain a sense of community and connection, which was crucial to student mental health. Teachers' work with school administrators, parents, and students affects participative management [35]. Teachers backed student-centered policies, advised on distant learning, and participated in lockdown decisions that affected education. Their participation meant that educational institutions could meet the needs of all stakeholders, supporting an inclusive and accountable management approach.

[36] noted that the Covid-19 pandemic underlined teachers' crucial role in crisis management and participatory education. Their quickness, care for students, and collaboration helped ensure educational continuity and design appropriate policies. Recognising and supporting teachers during lockdowns is essential for building resilient educational institutions that value variety, creativity, and fair access to learning.

Impact of Lockdowns on Curricular Implementation in South African Primary Schools

[37] claim that teachers, students, parents, and educational authorities have to work together to execute the curriculum during the pandemic in participative management. This technique adjusts the curriculum to meet student needs while maintaining educational standards. Adaptability, comprehensiveness, and input are crucial. Thus, integrating stakeholders in decision-making improves curricular change efficiency and fosters accountability and

ownership. Covid-19 lockdowns disrupted traditional classrooms, forcing a rapid move to remote learning [38]. This change has highlighted educational resource disparities in South Africa. Unfortunately, many rural primary schools lacked dependable internet connectivity and digital resources for online learning [39]. This technology gap has hindered primary school lessons and communication.

Globally, the pandemic highlighted the critical role of good communication in ensuring educational continuity. In South Africa, the lack of direct engagement between students and their teachers impeded the participatory management approach since opportunities for collaborative decision-making and real-time feedback were nonexistent [40]. The isolation of teaching practice students from their mentors and classmates exacerbated these challenges by decreasing the quality of mentorship and support required during these challenging periods.

It is crucial to invest in digital infrastructure, such as reliable internet access and digital devices for every school, in order to bridge the digital gap and address these challenges. [41] assert that providing training for teachers, students, and parents on the appropriate utilisation of these tools is undeniably vital. Implementing a hybrid learning strategy that integrates online and in-person techniques can provide flexibility and maintain consistent educational standards for primary schools. Creating virtual platforms for cooperation and feedback can effectively uphold the concepts of participatory management [42]. Regular virtual meetings and online forums can promote ongoing connection and involvement among stakeholders. Virtual mentorship programs can enhance support systems for teaching practice students, offering them essential guidance and support. By making specific investments and engaging in strategic planning, South African primary schools can effectively handle these difficulties, ensuring better execution of the curriculum and maintaining good communication even amid disruptions [43].

Curriculum Transformation During Lockdown in Primary Schools

The Covid-19 lockdowns prompted a swift curriculum transformation in primary schools throughout the globe. Teachers rapidly responded to online learning environments by using electronic resources and platforms that ensured educational continuity. For example, in Finland and Singapore, where digital infrastructure was robust, schools seamlessly shifted to virtual classrooms with advanced e-learning systems and interactive software. Students successfully engaged in both synchronous and asynchronous learning, utilising digital resources and participating in virtual group activities. Conversely, in South Africa, the digital divide caused substantial challenges, particularly in rural areas where reliable internet connectivity and digital gadgets were scarce [38]. As a result, South African teachers reduced inequities by using alternate techniques including educational radio and television broadcasts to reach students who did not have access to online learning. Similarly, printed learning materials were supplied to ensure that all students may continue their education in the absence of digital resources [37]. These innovative methods emphasised the necessity of adaptability and creativity in curriculum delivery, highlighting the need for equal access to educational technology to bridge knowledge and content gaps and support different learning environments during crises.

Lockdown Challenges in South African Primary Schools

Lockdowns during the Covid-19 outbreak significantly impacted primary schools worldwide, particularly in South Africa. The swift shift to remote learning exposed and worsened educational inequalities, with many students lacking technology and reliable internet access. Teachers, often untrained in digital platforms, struggled to adapt, affecting instructional quality [11]. In South Africa, the digital divide and socioeconomic disparities hindered remote learning, particularly in rural areas [42]. Wealthy schools transitioned more smoothly, deepening educational inequities. The psychological toll on students and teachers, including anxiety and stress, further complicated the situation. Parents, especially in low-income families, faced challenges balancing work and their children's education [13].

Impact on the Quality of Teaching and Learning

Lockdowns have harmed education worldwide and South Africa as well. The digital gap and teacher unpreparedness have caused education quality to vary. Thus, primary school students without online resources fall further behind, exacerbating educational inequities. [5] claim that the lack of face-to-face encounters impeded the development of critical skills like analytical thinking, problem-solving, and interpersonal involvement. Thus, primary schooling promotes students' social and emotional development as well as intellectual learning. [37] note that students lack these vital experiences due to the lack of classrooms. In addition, inconsistent remote learning has lowered school quality. Online classrooms have often imitated traditional classroom approaches without properly using digital tools to promote learning. This approach reduces student engagement and motivation.

Mitigation strategies

Covid-19 pandemic challenges requires a multi-faceted approach that involves significant investment in educational infrastructure, teacher training and support systems for students and parents which encompasses the following:

[41] suggest that governments and educational stakeholders prioritise digital infrastructure to eliminate the digital gap and provide all students with dependable internet and electronic gadgets. Thus, public-private collaborations can help underprivileged groups. Teachers need extensive training and ongoing professional development to integrate digital materials into the curriculum and develop innovative remote learning practices.

[28] suggests blended learning methods that include online and face-to-face learning for flexibility and continuity during disturbances. Include social-emotional learning in the curriculum to increase student well-being. Parents need training, internet resources, and helplines to help their children with remote learning.

Mizrak (2024) suggests that authorities develop strong alternative ways to mitigate future education sector disruptions. These programs should include remote learning protocols to let students continue their education despite obstacles. According to [16], educational equity must be maintained to guarantee that all students have equal access to resources and support. During emergencies, education quality monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are crucial. This is needed to identify and fix learning issues and improve response efficiency.

PURPOSE

The article examines the influence of Covid -19 on the efficacy of participative management in primary schools.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The main question is: “To what extent does Covid -19 influence the efficacy of participative management in primary schools?”

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Contingency Theory of Leadership (CTL) serves as the theoretical foundation for analysing the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the efficacy of participatory management in primary schools. This theory suggests that effective leadership is dependent upon a range of both internal and external factors, including the environment, the organisational structure, and the circumstances (Fiedler, 1964). Amidst the Covid-19 pandemic, school administrators had to adapt their management approaches to solve the challenges presented by distant learning and social estrangement protocols [10]. The Contingency Theory elucidates the significance of adaptable and flexible leadership techniques in maintaining participative management under adversarial situations. Researchers can utilise this framework to examine the responses of various schools to the Covid-19 crisis. They can then determine which adaptive strategies were the most successful in maintaining stakeholder engagement and collaborative decision-making processes in primary schools [45].

METHOD

This qualitative study uses a systematic literature review of scholarly books and articles published from 2016 to 2024 to explore the influence of COVID-19 on participative management in primary schools. [45] describe integrative literature reviews as research that critiques and synthesizes literature to generate new perspectives. This type of review allows for the combination and synthesis of findings. The analysis employed an interpretivist paradigm within a local context, acknowledging social and cultural limitations [46]. Reflections are based on the authors subjective perspectives.

Data collection

The systematic literature review examined the influence of Covid-19 on participative management in primary schools, using sources from 2016-2024. This analysis focused on scholarly books and articles to understand how participative management strategies were adapted during the pandemic, particularly in rural primary schools. It highlighted the impact on teacher and student well-being and dignity, contributing valuable insights to effective management practices during crises.

Data analysis

The analysis of literature on "Examining the Influence of the Covid-19 Pandemic on the Efficacy of Participative Management in Primary Schools" uses an interpretivist paradigm, as noted by [46]. This approach recognizes the social and cultural foundations of school settings and the limitations of objective analysis. Embracing subjective perspectives, the author examines interpersonal dynamics, community norms, and power structures to understand participative management during the pandemic. This interpretive lens provides insights

crucial for developing effective, tailored interventions for primary schools during crises like Covid-19.

DISCUSSION

The Covid-19 epidemic has had a profound influence on the educational sphere, particularly in the management of primary schools. The above statement is supported by the article titled "Deepening Divides or Inciting Change?" "Ongoing Impacts of Covid-19 on Teaching and Learning" [47]. which investigated the enduring consequences of the pandemic on the processes of teaching and learning consequently, the administration of primary schools. An important concern emphasized in the paper was the increasing disparity in access to digital technology. The transition to remote and hybrid schooling amid the epidemic has exacerbated pre-existing disparities in technology and internet access, especially in underprivileged regions [47]. This has ramifications for participatory management as it becomes increasingly difficult for school administrators to actively engage all stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and students in decision-making processes. Moreover, the study highlights that the epidemic has resulted in heightened levels of stress and burnout among educators [47]. This might impede school leaders in cultivating a collaborative and participatory atmosphere as instructors may exhibit reduced engagement or resistance towards assuming extra duties.

In resolving these difficulties, the article proposes that school administrators should modify their management strategies to become more adaptable and receptive to the changing requirements of their school communities [47]. This may entail investigating novel methods of enabling collaborative decision-making such as leveraging digital tools and platforms. In summary, the article emphasises the importance of school leaders using proactive and inventive measures in managing participative management to ensure its effectiveness amidst the continued effects of the Covid-19 pandemic.

The Covid-19 pandemic has had a profound effect on the efficacy of participatory management in primary schools. The pandemic has posed challenges to participative management, which entails the active involvement of teachers and occasionally students in decision-making processes. A major obstacle we have faced is the absence of alternate methods to involve children and teachers in instructional activities while they are confined during the lockdown period. Due to the shift to remote or hybrid learning models the conventional approaches to engaging stakeholders in school management have become less efficient [47]. The geographical separation and the requirement for maintaining social distance posed challenges in organizing in-person meetings, collaborative workshops, and other interactive activities that are crucial for successful participatory management [47].

Moreover, the heightened strain and stress encountered by teachers within the pandemic also impeded their capacity to actively engage in school administration [47]. Teachers faced limited time and energy to participate in decision-making due to the demands of adapting to new teaching methods, managing distant learning, and addressing students' social-emotional needs [48]. Nevertheless, certain schools have exhibited tenacity and successfully upheld the efficacy of participative management despite the challenges. For example, several educational institutions have utilised digital technologies to enable virtual meetings, collaborative decision-making, and the sharing of information [48]. Previous efforts have prioritised the development of more robust means of communication and the cultivation of a

shared feeling of belonging among individuals with a vested interest even within the context of remote learning [47].

Moreover, the Covid-19 pandemic has greatly tested the efficacy of participative management in primary schools. The absence of alternative strategies to involve students and instructors together with the heightened workload and stress faced by educational professionals has posed challenges in sustaining the necessary degree of stakeholder engagement for effective participatory management. Nevertheless, several educational institutions have displayed resilience and adjusted their participatory management strategies to the current circumstances, indicating that innovative solutions and a steadfast emphasis on communication and community are key. Hence, the efficacy of participatory management can be sustained despite the presence of exceptional obstacles.

CONCLUSION

The Covid-19 pandemic exposed notable challenges and opportunities for participatory governance in primary schools. Conversely, conventional in-face to face relationships were disrupted and many schools effectively implemented digital tools to uphold stakeholder participation and facilitate collaborative decision-making in primary schools [49]. The aforementioned experiences underscored the significance of adaptive and resilient management structures within educational institutions. To improve participative management in primary schools and better prepare them for future disruptions, it is beneficial to integrate technological solutions with conventional practices. This integration can create a more inclusive and dynamic decision-making environment, as suggested by [50].

RECOMMENDATIONS

Undoubtedly, these scholars [48] recommend that school leaders and stakeholders ought to provide urgent attention and comprehensive intervention strategies as required to mitigate the long-term effects of these sequelae on teachers and students' educational trajectory. In response to the psychological impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on teachers and students, school leaders are expected to prioritize targeted mental health programs and provide relevant counselling strategies to curb such sequelae [51]. [52] also recommended integrating counselling services, support groups, and related workshops to handle teachers and students' anxiety, tension, and trauma to prevent ineffective participatory management in schools. Thus, the principal must create a supportive and emotionally stable environment for effective participative management in primary schools by addressing the emotional well-being of students and teachers.

Similarly, school leaders and stakeholders should actively invest in and improve the technological infrastructure to reduce potential barriers to collaborative decision-making in schools. Thus, [53] observed that fair access to digital tools, training, and digital literacy among stakeholders can improve decision-making collaboration. [52] also urge principals to create a technologically capable environment that enhances participative management and mitigates pandemic challenges by developing resilient and agile educational leadership frameworks.

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